

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Salinity tolerance of some *Azolla* spp.

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Soil salinity is a serious problem for rice culture in many coastal areas of southern India. If azolla is to be used in these areas, it must be screened for salinity tolerance.

In a greenhouse study, we tested the salinity tolerance of five *Azolla* spp. by artificially salinizing the soil to 5 and 8 dS/m. Soil (5 kg) in shallow pots (45 cm diam, 20 cm deep) with 10 cm standing water was inoculated with 5 g azolla (fresh weight). The experiment had three replications, with nonsalinized soil as control. The fresh weight of azolla fronds was recorded 30 d after inoculation (see table).

Soil salinity decreased biomass production in all of the species. *A. microphylla* and *A. mexicana* had greater tolerance for salinity than *A. pinnata* and *A. filiculoides*. The study indicates the potential of *A. mexicana* and *A. microphylla* for use as a biofertilizer in saline rice soils. The mechanism for salinity tolerance of the two species needs further study. ■

Effect of salinity on the growth of azolla species.

<i>Azolla</i> species	Azolla (g fresh wt /0.16 m ²) at indicated soil salinity level (dS/m)			
	0.3 (control)	5.0	8.0	Mean ^a
<i>A. caroliniana</i>	51.30	34.34	4.72	30.12
<i>A. pinnata</i>	49.80	35.37	2.77	29.31
<i>A. filiculoides</i>	41.63	21.80	4.70	22.71
<i>A. mexicana</i>	72.10	50.07	18.60	46.72
<i>A. microphylla</i>	81.40	51.53	21.73	51.65
LSD (P = 0.05)				
<i>Azolla</i> species	3.50			
Salinity levels	4.70			

^aMean of 3 treatments

Rock phosphate is an effective P carrier for azolla

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P fertilizer is the most critical and costly input for the cultivation of rice and azolla. Most soils used for growing rice in AP are P deficient, which adversely affects the multiplication of azolla. Single superphosphate (SSP) at 8.8 kg P/ha is recommended for growing azolla, but SSP is expensive. We investigated using rock phosphate (RP), which is a less expensive source of P than SSP.

In a greenhouse experiment, we added 4.4, 8.8, and 17 kg P/ha as SSP (16%

water-soluble P₂O₅) and RP (21% total P₂O₅) to a Vertisol that had 8.8 kg native P/ha. Combinations of SSP and RP to supply 4.4 + 4.4, 2.9 + 5.9, and 2.2 + 6.6 kg P/ha were also used.

Fronds of *A. caroliniana* and *A. pinnata* (Rajendranagar strain) were inoculated at 10 g fresh weight/pot (45 cm diam, 20-cm-deep, containing 5 kg soil). Each treatment was replicated three times. The fronds were harvested, blotted on absorbent paper, and weighed to get the fresh weight of azolla 30 d after inoculation (see table).

Azolla responded positively to both P sources. Equal biomass was produced using up to 8.8 kg P/ha as SSP and up to 17 kg P/ha as RP. Of all the combinations of SSP + RP tested, 1:1 was best, which was on par with the two treatments above. RP can be used as a total or partial substitute for SSP, thus reducing the cost of inputs for azolla. ■

Efficiency of single superphosphate and phosphate rock as P source for azolla.

P treatment	Azolla biomass production (g fresh wt/0.16 m ²)		Mean ^a
	<i>A. caroliniana</i>	<i>A. pinnata</i>	
Control	61.8	49.4	51.6
SSP 4.4 kg P/ha	88.7	68.1	78.4
SSP 8.8 kg P/ha	148.1	104.0	126.0
SSP 17 kg P/ha	152.4	111.5	132.0
PR 4.4 kg P/ha	78.5	79.1	78.8
PR 8.8 kg P/ha	97.7	93.1	95.4
PR 17 kg P/ha	120.7	119.1	123.9
SSP ^b + PR 1:1	154.7	100.1	127.4
SSP ^b + PR 1:2	124.7	100.2	112.5
SSP ^b + PR 1:3	86.9	105.9	96.4
Mean	112.2	93.1	
LSD (P = 0.05) <i>Azolla</i> species		3.8	
Treatments		8.4	

^aMean of 3 replications. ^bAt 8.8 kg P/ha.

Influences of soybean N fixation on soil N balance in rice - soybean rotation

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Soybean has a significant role in maintaining the soil N fertility in rice - soybean cropping systems. We examined the effects of soybean N fixation on N

fertility of the ricefield in a rice - soybean rotation.

The experiment was conducted in a sandy loam San Sai soil with pH 5.7-5.9 and 0.05-0.06% total N from Chiang Mai, Thailand (19° N, 99° E), from Aug 1988 to Apr 1989. Chiang Mai has a definite wet season (WS) and dry season (DS). The nine treatments included a factorial combination of N fertilizer applied to rice

N balance for soybean grown after rice fertilized at 3 N levels, and supplied with 3 levels of starter N. Chiang Mai, Thailand, 1988-89.

Treatment	N (kg/ha)				N balance ^b	
	Total ^a	In seed	In straw + seed	Fixed	Seed only ^c	Seed + straw ^d
R0						
S0	145	122	135	122	0 ab	-13 ab
S25	164	133	152	132	-1 bc	-20 bc
S50	169	131	155	140	9 a	-15 ab
R100						
S0	164	133	152	138	5 ab	-14 ab
S25	166	134	155	134	0 ab	-21 bc
S50	168	134	155	130	-4 bc	-25 cd
R300						
S0	169	130	145	139	9 a	-6 a
S25	170	133	155	136	3 ab	-19 bc
S50	179	138	163	128	-10 c	-35 d

^aIncludes fallen leaves; did not include roots and nodules. ^bMeans having a common letter in a column are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance. ^cN fixed = seed N. ^dN fixed = seed N + straw N.

cultivar RD21 at 0 (R0), 100 (R100), and 300 (R300) kg N/ha and to the following soybean cultivar SJ5 at 0 (S0), 25 (S25), and 50 (S50) kg N/ha. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with six replications. Rice was transplanted in WS. Soybean inoculated with *Bradyrhizobium*

japonicum was sown in DS after the rice was harvested. We measured N fixation in soybean using the xylem-sap method.

The amount of N fixed was either similar to or exceeded the amount of N removed in the harvested soybean seed. A little N was left after seed harvest in some treatments (R0S50, R100S0, R300S0,

R300S25). If soybean straw was also removed at harvest, a net N loss occurred in all treatments.

When the rice crop was not fertilized with N, net soil N depletion decreased with increasing levels of starter N. But with 100 and 300 kg N/ha, the net depletion of N increased with increasing levels of starter N for soybean. The net soil N depletion was estimated to range from -1 kg N/ha in R0S25 to -10 kg N/ha in R300S50. The net depletion of soil N ranged from -6 kg N/ha in R300S0 to -35 kg N/ha in R300S50 if straw N removal was also considered (see table).

Soil N balance was significantly different among treatments after seed was harvested. Small amounts of N were left in the soil at moderate N levels; at low N levels, fixed N was equal to removed N. A negative N balance was found at high N levels. When straw was also removed (a normal practice in the Chiang Mai Valley), a negative N balance was found in each treatment, which means the soil N pool was depleted. Thus soybean crops in rice - soybean cropping systems appear to reduce soil N. ■

Sugar beet tops as green manure for rice

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In subtropical northwestern India, farmers have started to cultivate sugar beet as a winter crop followed by rice. Sugar beet tops under these conditions can contain 100 kg N/ha or more.

We conducted an experiment for 2 yr to determine the usefulness of sugar beet tops as green manure on a sandy loam soil having pH 8.2, 0.35% organic C, 0.03% total N, 195 kg available N/ha (alkaline potassium permanganate extractable), 13.2 kg available P/ha, and 90 kg available K/ha. The treatments tested in a randomized block design were 0, 60, 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha as urea alone and 0, 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha along with sugar beet tops.

Sugar beet tops amounting to 35 t/ha (av regional yield of variety Ramonskaya-06) containing 89 kg N/ha in the first year and 91 kg N/ha in the

second were chopped at harvest (about 45 d before transplanting of rice) and incorporated into the soil for the treatments. Inorganic N was applied in three equal splits as per treatment. A basal uniform dose of 13 kg P and 25 kg K/ha was applied before PR106 seedlings were transplanted. The rice crop was irrigated. Data were pooled for the 2 yr.

Incorporation of sugar beet tops increased rice grain yield in both the absence and presence of urea N (Table 1). Statistically, grain yield increased up to 90 kg N/ha in soils amended with tops and up to 120 kg N/ha without tops. Sugar beet tops without urea N increased yield by 52% over control. The yield obtained with 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha with tops were at par with those obtained at higher N levels of 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha (Table 1).

The rice grain yield (y), when regressed on the urea N levels (N), gave the following best model, which was significant at 1% level of probability:

Table 1. Rice grain yield without and with sugar beet top incorporation. Punjab, India.^a

Urea N rate (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Without tops	With tops
0	2.2	3.4
60	4.1	5.5
90	5.2	6.2
120	6.3	6.8
150	6.5	-
LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.6

^aMean of 2 yr.

Table 2. Predicted urea N equivalents and apparent N recovery from sugar beet tops. Punjab, India.

Urea N rate (kg/ha)	Predicted urea N equivalent (kg/ha)	Apparent N recovery (%) from sugar beet tops
0	32	20
60	39	32
90	40	27
120	35	25
Mean	37	26